

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF EMPLOYEE'S ATTITUDE IN ORGANIZATION CULTURE IN HYUNDAI

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Abstract:

Organizational culture received much attention over a long period of time, due to its effect potential impact on the organization success. Organization culture is critical factor in enhancing employee job attitude. This study examined the impact of three methods such as autocratic, technocratic and bureaucratic off employee attitude in the organization. The employees of the company have been responded of the study. The population size is 90 employee of HR department, out of which only 57 employees have responded which is used sample in this study. Data was collected through the opinion standardized questionnaires measuring. Structured questioner used as research instrument for collecting data from the responses. The data was the screened and use for data analysis. The data analysis used statistical spss version 25. From the analysis of the study it was found that attitude has significant co-relation with education qualification and experiences, the other finding discussing in detail in the respectively chapters

Keywords: Employee attitude, Organization culture, Sustainable development, Employee wellbeing.

INTRODUCTION:

Employees attitude impacts organizational culture in negative as well as positive way, positive attitude helps in the well being of the people which impacts the growth of the organisation. If an employee projects a positive attitude towards their co workers it will be easy to communicate and to achieve the goals in a better way. By developing a positive attitude, individuals tend to cope up with stressful situations and they also accomplish their personal and organizational goals. Organizational culture is reflected in the way employees behave in the workplace and the way they get along with their co workers. So, in order to have a better organizational culture, a positive and enthusiastic attitude is necessary. Similar researches have been conducted by many authors (Benita, 2021; Monica, 2021; Kumar, 2020; Kumar & Shree, 2019; Monica & Supriya, 2019; Mahesh & Uma Rani, 2019; Mahesh, Gigi, & Uma Rani, 2019; Robert & Monisha, 2019; Kumar & Shree, 2018).

OBJECTIVES:

Primary:

1. To study the impact of employee's attitude in organization culture.

Secondary:

1. To study the work environment relating to employee's attitude.
2. To study the preference exiting in work culture
3. To provide suitable suggestions for healthy organization culture.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Hofstede (1985) studied cross-cultural work data on employee attitude includes 67 countries, according to Hofstede (1980, 1985). Individualism-collectivism, uncertainty avoidance vs. risk taking, power distance, and masculinity/femininity were among the four aspects he discovered. Understanding cross-cultural differences in four dimensions is a beneficial framework for employee attitude. It also acknowledges the importance of cultural factors on employee attitudes. However, recent studies have revealed that a person's country/culture is not just a powerful predictor of employee attitudes, but also a person's work type (Saari, 2000; Saari & Erez, 2002; Saari & Schneider, 2001)

Robbins (2003) evaluative assertions that might be positive or negative in relation to objects, people, or events. As a result, they represent ones feelings regarding something. Beneficial remarks may have positive impacts on the thing, person, or event in question, whilst negative words may have bad consequences. A person's attitude is a positive or bad feeling or mental state of readiness that is acquired and organized via experience and has a specific impact on how they respond to people, objects, and circumstances. Managers should be aware of the significance of this definition of attitude. Attitudes are first acquired. Second, one's predispositions toward specific features of the environment are defined by one's attitudes. Third, attitudes serve as the emotional foundation for interpersonal relationships and social identification. Fourth, attitudes are well-organized and linked to the essence of a person's personality. Some attitudes are steadfast and permanent; nonetheless, attitudes, like all psychological variables, are vulnerable to change.

Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller (2012) Employment attitudes are evaluations of one's job that represent one's feelings, convictions, and loyalty to it. Despite the fact that academics have previously discovered a variety of employee attitudes, work satisfaction and commitment are the most widely used and researched.

Allport (1935) attitude is defined as a mental or neural state of readiness that is organized by experience and has a directive or dynamic influence on an individual's response to all objects and situations with which it is associated. A mindset or a tendency to respond in a certain way as a result of an individual's experience and temperament is a simpler definition of attitude.

Harrison & Stokes (1992) All members of an organization's culture shape their views and attitudes, as well as their behaviour and, most crucially, their performance. It has an impact on the entire organizational life, including decision-making processes, recruitment, promotion, and reward systems, as well as external systems in general. Internally, how people are handled, how customers are treated, and how a firm respond to its surroundings

Mahler, 1997 ,Employee attitudes are influenced by organizational culture, which provides a reservoir of organizational meanings against which results, experience, and performance data are interpreted, as well as enquiries regarding changes in processes and programmer technologies.

Lok& crawford, 2004 Companies must ensure that managers at all levels keep in touch with their workers. This is to convey the company's values, vision, direction, and goals to employees so that they are completely aware of the organization's ongoing procedures. Employees will feel appreciated and have authority in the workplace as a result of this.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Descriptive research design was used for this research. Data was collected by using self-structured questionnaire constructed with five-point Likert's scale. The questionnaire is circulated to 57 employees using convinces sampling method. The collected data is analyzed using frequency, mean analysis, t-test and Anova.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Table 1: Classification of Responce based on Age

S.NO	AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
1.	18 - 25	43	74.4
2.	25-35	14	24.6
3.	35-50	0	0
4.	TOTAL	57	100

From the above table it could be found that more than 74.4% of the respondents are in the age group of 18-25 years.

Table 2: Classification of Responce based on Gender

S.NO	GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
1.	MALE	34	59.6
2.	FEMALE	23	40.4
3.	TOTAL	57	100

From the above table it could be found that 59.6 percent of respondents are male Employees and 40.4 percent of respondents are female Employees

Table 3: Classification of Responce based on marital status

S.NO	MARITAL STATUS	NUMBERS	PERCENT
1.	MARRIED	9	15.8
2.	UNMARRIED	48	84.2
	TOTAL	57	100

From the above table it could be inferred that majority of the respondents were unmarried, which is 82.4 percentage.

Table 4: Classification of Respondence based on Education qualification

S.NO	EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	UG	34	59.6
2	PG	19	33.3
3	PH.D	4	7.0
	Total	55	100

From the above table, the majority of data is completed from under graduate Employees with the percentage of 59.6.

Table 5: Classification of Respondence based on Monthly Income

S.NO	PARTICULAR	NO OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
1	Below 25,000	35	61.4
2	25,000 – 50,000	21	36.8
3	50,000 – 70,0000	1	1.8
4	Above 75,000	0	0
	TOTAL	57	100

From the above table, the majority of data is completed from Below 25,000 monthly income with the percentage of 61.4% Employee.

Table 6: Classification of Respondence based on Employee Experience

S.NO	EMPLOYEE EXPERIENCE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	LESS THAN 1 YEAR	28	49.1
2	1 TO 3 YEAR	11	19.3
3	3 TO 5 YEAR	14	24.6
4	5 YEAR ABOVE	4	7.0
	TOTAL	57	100

From the above table, the majority of data is completed from Less than 1 year of Employee Experience with the percentage of 49.1% of Employees.

Independent sample T test

Analysis of difference on being rule orientated based on Gender.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significance difference between gender and marital status with respect to employee attitude in workplace.

Alternative Hypothesis:

There is a significance difference between gender and marital status with respect to employee attitude in workplace.

Table 7: Independent sample T test

S. No	Perception of Employee Attitude at Work Place	Gender		Marital Status	
		T-Value	Sig value	T-Value	Sig value
1	The Employees are recognized in the company for their achievement	0.395	0.395	2.626	0.011*
2	In your company, employees work life balance is encouraged	0.835	0.835	1.546	0.128
3	Management helps to resolve in work related area	0.853	0.853	1.212	0.231
4	The employees can feel stress in job frequently	0.965	0.965	0.416	0.679
5	Employees receives adequate recognition for their work	0.339	0.339	1.579	0.120
6	Special training is offered by the company to uplift the employees skills	0.858	0.858	0.451	0.654
7	The company provides good salary hike on every year for employees	0.315	0.315	0.256	0.799
8	In the company , the employees cooperative in all aspects	0.748	0.748	0.336	0.738
9	The company will take decision on employees considerations	0.945	0.945	0.881	0.382
10	The company discuss the issues before making the decision	0.411	0.411	1.503	0.139

***5 % Level of significance**

In this table, the test we have used is independent sample t test and the results are tabulated in the table above. The values obtained are greater than 0.05, which indicates that there is no relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Table 8: Anova analysis

Analysis of difference on sharing information freely based on age

S. No	Perception of Employee Attitude at Work Place	Age	
		F-Value	Sig value
1	The Employees are recognized in the company for their achievement	1.300	0.259
2	In your company, employees work life balance is encouraged	0.486	0.489
3	Management helps to resolve in work related area	0.072	0.789
4	The employees can feel stress in job frequently	0.112	0.739
5	Employees receives adequate recognition for their work	0.012	0.914
6	Special training is offered by the company to uplift the employees skills	0.019	0.891
7	The company provides good salary hike on every year for employees	4.086	0.048
8	In the company , the employees cooperative in all aspects	0.959	0.332
9	The company will take decision on employees considerations	0.562	0.457
10	The company discuss the issues before making the decision	0.251	0.619

In this ANOVA, the independent variable is Age level. Table 8 shows the significance value of ANOVA. In this case, most of the value is greater than 0.05, so there are no relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

CONCLUSION:

Employee attitude is one of the most major factor that impacts the growth and welfare of an organization. Positive attitude is necessary in order to help the organization to achieve its common and individual goals. In this article , we have found out that employee attitude is suite important as it helps the coworkers to mingle with each other and improve their work to a certain extent so that the quality of the work is increased which in turn increases the growth of the organization. A good attitude is necessary so that it will be easy to communicate for the betterment of our self and the people working along with us

SUGGESTIONS:

1. A company should work for welfare workers and a profit organization
2. Sometimes employees work based on their customer
3. Employee should be trained about the working culture
4. They need to consider employees plans.
5. Ambience can be improved
6. As per employee point of view. Corporate should considered as a employees development
7. Monetary reward system needs to be retain
8. Need some better hike as per the achievements by the employees
9. Encourage the employee
10. Every organization unique, and there is a diff between firm and the superior, everyone is not directly reporting to the manager there is architect., so it depends the fund position of organization, heads, superiors, and co executives.
11. The company's organization Structure could be more well defined with more autonomy to employees
12. Be Smart worker not a hard worker
13. The above mentioned questions are related to the current working organization
14. Now a day all organization are centralized but some of the organization are good.

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